

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF IMPARTING FIRE-RETARDANT PROPERTIES TO INSULATING MATERIALS MADE OF NATURAL FIBERS

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Abstract

At the moment, there is an increasing problem in the world with the creation of fire-safe building materials. Most fires occur instantly, due to the use of highly flammable insulation material from refined petroleum products. Polymer materials without flame retardants burn well, as a result of which the flame covers the walls of buildings. Industrial flame retardants based on chlorine and fluorine are poisonous. Toxic gases are released during the combustion of this material.

This article discusses the issue of conferring flame retardant properties with environmentally friendly flame retardants. Such flame retardants can be based on nitrogen and phosphorus. At the same time, getting into the environment, they do not cause harm. Such substances are capable of decomposition under real conditions. They also do not emit poison when burning and are safe for humans.

Keywords: Flame retardant, anti-fire insulation material, natural fiber, fiber insulation, anti-fire properties.

The problem of the safety of thermal insulation materials. Insulation materials are used everywhere. But the materials used have disadvantages - a great fire hazard and a tendency to catch fire. In 2021 year, 12,256 fires occurred in the Republic of Kazakhstan, as a result of which 413 people died, damage amounted to more than 9 billion tenge. Most thermal insulation is combustible materials, which provokes the risk of fire. [1].

Flame Retardants – what is it. Flame retardants are additional substances that reduce the flammability of materials. They provide self-attenuation. [2][4]. Principles of chemical action of flame retardants. [2][3]:

1. When the temperature rises, flame retardants decompose into non-flammable gas and other substances, while heat from the burning material is absorbed. This will lower the temperature and reduce the amount of oxygen.

2. Some flame retardants are charred, creating incombustible gases and coke, which forms a thermal insulation layer on the surface.

3. Other flame retardants work as inhibitors of the oxidation of organic substances.

Biological flame retardants. Flame retardants can be created from natural raw materials – biological flame retardants. In the studies of these authors. [5][6], starch, chitosan and cyclodextrin were used to create safe insulation materials.

1. Starch, a representative of biological flame retardants. It promotes self-damping during gorenje. [7].

2. Tannic acid is used in the processing of porous materials, it is characterized by cheapness and accessibility. Such compounds create a carbon coke layer. Which in turn stops the access of oxygen and the access of heat. At the same time, iron and nickel catalyze this process. A weak gas is released and the oxidation process stops. [7].

3. Cyclodextrin is not an expensive bio-flame retardant. It also forms a carbon protective layer, ammonia, and water vapor, which do not support combustion. [7].

4. Phytic acid from the same class of flame retardants. It contains 28% atomic phosphorus in the form of phosphate groups. Metals work as a catalyst. [7].

5. Chitosan is used in a mixture of flame retardants, with the addition of aluminum and hypophosphite. Hydroxyl groups and nitrogen form ammonia, thereby

reducing the concentration of oxygen in the air mixture. [7].

6. Lignin with natural origin has flame retardant properties. Its interaction with flame retardants during combustion creates a layer of silicon and carbon. [8].

7. Polydopamine is a flame retardant with adhesive properties. It is environmentally friendly. A catalyst in the form of nickel and iron contributes to this process. [9-10].

Bulging flame retardants. The swelling flame retardant works as follows. A porous coke layer with a density of is formed on the surface $3 \times 10^{-3} - 3 \times 10^{-2} \text{ g/cm}^3$, while the volume increases quite strongly. The thermal conductivity of such an insulating layer is commensurate with the thermal conductivity of the air. At the same time, the heat from the fire does not fit the material. Heat transfer is reduced by 100 times. Also, the oxygen of the air cannot reach the material. When such a porous layer is formed, endothermic reactions occur, which in turn take away heat, thereby significantly reducing the temperature of the medium. At a temperature of 210 °C, ammonium polyphosphate is phosphorylated to form essential phosphorus groups. [11]. The authors studied the effectiveness of a swelling flame retardant on textiles using a solution of carbamide, pentaerythritol and ammonium phosphate. Such flame-retardant coatings are quite thin, this does not affect the size of the processed material. [12].

Hemp fiber is an excellent material for insulation. The cannabis plant is common in a wide variety of countries. The authors of the study added hemp fiber to drywall slabs. Further, they came to the conclusion that by adding only 2% hemp fiber, it is possible to reduce the density and increase the thermal insulation properties to a significant extent. [13]. The authors of the study tested 11 samples with a thickness of 50 mm and an area of 100×100 mm, which were prepared under conditions of 50% humidity and 23 °C. insulation for thermal conductivity and fire resistance, having a density of 40 kg/m³. Anti-fire characteristics were determined using the LST EN ISO 11925-2 method. The flammability of the material when it enters the flame was investigated. Flame retardants Apyrol BKW and Flovan CGN applied to the samples by immersion and spraying were used for the study. To prevent the ignition of hemp fiber, 45 g/l of flame retardant is required. The mass of the sample should not change after ignition, which confirms the absence of combustion. The added poly lactide fiber melts, filling the space, thereby reducing the rate of ignition. The vapor permeability of insulation samples was studied using the LST EN 12086 C method. To increase the water-repellent properties, the hydrophobic agent Beiphob FR with a concentration of 1.25 g/l was used. The vapor permeability coefficient of the untreated sample was 1.72, and after treatment - 1.8. [14]. With the help of FOX 304 equipment, a decrease in thermal conductivity by 3.8% was investigated when adding 11% poly lactide to hemp fiber. Also, the thermal conductivity decreased by 4.4% with the addition of 15% poly lactide. [15]. The authors' study compared the possibilities of rotting and the use of hemp shavings and fiber insulation in construction. Hemp fibers can be produced in three stages: rolling

crushing into fibers and grinding to a fiber length of 20-30 mm. The binding component in the authors' study was corn starch. It is safe, but hygroscopic, and requires hydrophobization. The hydrophobic agent Beiphob FR was used for this purpose. The samples were formed thermally at 130 °C and rolled into rolls. Samples with 11 and 15% poly lactide were obtained with densities of 40 and 100 kg/m³. Samples from hemp shavings were produced at 160 °C. The properties of hemp insulation depend on the microscopic structure of the bonds. It was examined using a scanning electron microscope. Poly lactide fills the voids in the fibers during heat treatment by gluing them together. An increase in density by 2 times increases thermal conductivity by 4%. Mechanical characteristics show the highest strength with 15% poly lactide. The shavings insulation showed the highest strength characteristics, which is important for use in construction. Analyses have shown that treatment with a hydrophobic reagent significantly reduces water absorption. At a concentration of 0.75 g/l, water absorption decreases by 2 times, and at 1.25 g/l - by 20 times. For hemp shavings, the improvements were less noticeable: when using 16 g/l, water absorption decreased by 5.7 times, but unchanged at 8 g/l. [16][17].

Flame retardant thermal insulation materials are created from renewable sources. Thermal insulation materials can also be produced from renewable materials such as rice husks and wheat straw. This significantly reduces their cost, since raw materials are a waste of agricultural products. They will be completely environmentally friendly. [18]. The use of geopolymer glue in their production improves their properties, the ignition temperature increases. Geopolymer glue is a non-organic, non-flammable binder, provides a protective film on the surface of the fibers, which increases the fire resistance of the material. [19][21].

The use of silicon compounds to create refractory materials. The authors investigated the insulation made of porous vermiculite and liquid glass. The manufacturing process involves adding a modifier and a foaming agent to the liquid glass, after which the mixture is whipped in a mixer to stabilize the foam. Then vermiculite is added, and the solution is poured into plastic molds for solidification. The finished samples are kept for 3-28 days for subsequent tests. Granules of expanded vermiculite (brown or yellowish mica) are used as a filler, which increases in volume when moisture is absorbed. [22]. Inorganic flame retardant made of silicon dioxide does not harm the environment like halogens. But such a flame retardant is not suitable for polymers. Nano particles of silicon dioxide have a large surface area. And the binders are liquid glass, it binds the flame retardant particles to the processed material. [23].

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